

Extent of adaptation (indicated by arrows) of rice varieties and their yield potentials at varying depths and durations of waterlogged situations at vegetative and reproductive stages under direct-sown and transplanted conditions. West Bengal, India.

CNDW 332, CNDW 326, Jaisuria, CNDW 325, and CNDW 327 are only suitable for deep-water condition.

The results indicate that the genetic potential of individual varieties determines the ability to adjust to varying depths and durations of submergence under waterlogged conditions. Therefore, those traits can be introduced into improved varieties with greater yield potential. The figure gives information on varietal suitability for different low-lying, waterlogged situations. Grain characteristics of the promising varieties are available by contacting the authors.

Breeding for deep-water conditions

M. V. S. Sastry, T. E. Srinivasan, and U. Prasada Rao, All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Hyderabad 30, India

A breeding program to develop varieties suitable for deep-water conditions was initiated at the All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Hyderabad. Selections from the F₃ of the cross Rp 31-49-2 (short statured)/Leb Mue Nahng (tall, deep water-tolerant) — originally selected at AICRIP headquarters — were tested at the Deep Water Rice Research Station, Chagraghat, at a water depth of 70–80 cm for 1 month. On the basis of tolerance, 114 single-plant selections were made and further screened at Hyderabad, along with IRRI materials. Two sets of 100 of each entry were sown in four earthen pots. In the first set, 10-day-old seedlings remained submerged for 1 week in the drain at a water level of 150 cm. The percentage of seedlings that survived and their growth (in centimeters per day) during submergence were recorded. In the second set, 30-day-old seedlings were kept submerged. The performance of promising lines is summarized in the table.

The performance of promising lines screened for deep-water conditions. All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Hyderabad, India.

Designation	Cross	Seedlings submerged for 1 wk			
		10-day-old		30-day-old	
		survival (%)	Growth during submergence (cm/day)	Survival (%)	Growth during submergence (cm/day)
6204325	NP 31-49-2/ Leb Mue Nahng	94	2.9	91	2.9
6204314		81	2.4	90	3.3
6204435		90	0.4	87	3.1
KLG 6987-44-1	IR262/Khao Nahng Nuey	100	2.5	85	2.5
NP 31-492 (parent)	1 NP/Sigadis	0	0.0	41	0.6
Leb Mue Nahng	—	66	2.5	90	3.7